

EUPHRESCO

II

Modus operandi

Principles for a self-sustainable, long-term
cooperation consortium of phytosanitary
(statutory plant health) research programmes
owners and managers

Sixth Framework Programme

Document History

This document was first developed and published as part of the ERA-Net EUPHRESCO in 2010 (Deliverable 5.2). The document had the intention to give guidance for a self sustainable network after the end of EUPHRESCO.

EUPHRESCO was prolonged in EUPHRESCO II with new partners. Therefore there arose the need to evaluate and update the Modus operandi. In addition alternative futures for the network are discussed, which have to be considered in the document.

In 2012 questionnaires were sent to all EUPHRESCO partners asking for the evaluation of the existing Modus operandi. The following draft was presented and discussed at the project meeting in March 2013.

2013 ERA-Net EUPHRESCO II (European phytosanitary research coordination).

This document is part of the work programme of EUPHRESCO II, Deliverable 2.3.

EC 7th Framework programme ERA-Net scheme

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Distribution: All partners of EUPHRESCO, Governing Board, European Commission, EPPO

<http://www.euphresco.org>

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Introduction

The ERA-Net Project EUPHRESCO II is the continuance of EUPHRESCO, a policy-led coordination action, initiated by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS). The 3-year project started in January 2011, funded from the EU 7th framework programme. EUPHRESCO stands for **E**uropean **P**hytosanitary **R**esearch **C**ooperation and the project connects phytosanitary (statutory plant health) research funders (programme owners or managers) from 22 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Portugal, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and the UK.

The aim of both EUPHRESCO projects was to coordinate phytosanitary research at the European level. This involved coordination and co-operation between nationally-based phytosanitary research programmes in Europe for the first time through networking of research activities and a potential mutual opening or collaboration between national programmes. This coordination of national research has not been done significantly before EUPHRESCO nor has there been any significant trans-national funding of research, nor any alignment with EU-funded plant health research. EUPHRESCO therefore combines three main goals:

- Develop phytosanitary research policy and coordination at the EU-wide level.
- Optimise the research provision that underpins EU quarantine plant health policy development and implementation by reducing duplication and pooling resources.
- Increase the capacity of European phytosanitary science and research, in order to prevent the disappearance of EU expertise and maintain Europe's competitiveness in the global market. This supports EPPO's declaration of a *State of Emergency in Plant Health* in Madeira in 2004.

The projects were fully supported by the EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers for Plant Health Services (COPHS), The European Commission's Directorate General for Health and Consumer Protection (DG SANCO), the European Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), all of which have European plant health responsibilities.

One component of the work plan of EUPHRESCO and EUPHRESCO II is the establishment of a self-sustainable, long-term cooperation initiative (consortium or network) in Europe to ensure a durable coordination of European phytosanitary research. The initial basis for such a cooperation initiative has already been established through EUPHRESCO's activities since 2006.

The cooperation initiation shall represent a consortium of the EUPHRESCO partners, with the major aim to implement trans-national projects which might be of short duration, often pest specific and addressing regional issues, and responsive to emerging and urgent policy needs.

By comparison, EU-funded projects are more likely to be larger and/or more strategic projects, typically with a more EU-wide rationale. Furthermore this consortium should incorporate additional partners and establish sound contacts with other countries, e.g. USA (and its wider QUAD involving Australia, New Zealand and Canada) and various Mediterranean and African countries, especially International Cooperation Partner Countries. Similarly, collaboration with other organisations and other stakeholders is also important, as are linkages to different science areas that may have some influence on plant health issues, e.g., social sciences.

This modus operandi represents the proposed principles that will be necessary to initiate, operate and maintain a durable and self-sustainable cooperation initiative of phytosanitary research funders in Europe. It refers to the active participation of partners in cooperation, joint activities and the development of future phytosanitary research strategies, as well as other potential forms of cooperation. This Modus operandi does not represent fixed regulations and can be amended and adjusted during the future years if desired.

Scope of the document

This document describes the organisation and the main functions of the self-sustainable long-term cooperation initiative EUPHRESCO. This cooperation initiative will represent the transformation of the EU financed EUPHRESCO ERA-Net into a collaboration consortium of interested partners without EU funding.

This modus operandi is designed as a guide on the principles under which this collaboration consortium will operate, without legal binding, and covers the issues of administration as well as the implementation of trans-national projects.

Short definition of terms

Applied research	Original investigation undertaken in order to acquire new knowledge. It is, however, directed primarily towards a specific practical aim or objective support system
Basic/fundamental research	Experimental or theoretical work undertaken primarily to acquire new knowledge of the underlying foundation of phenomena and observable facts, without any particular application or use in view
ERA-Net	European Research Area – Networking, element of the FP6 specific programme aiming at integration and strengthening the European Research Area via coordination and mutual opening of national and regional research programmes
EUPHRESCO	EC sixth framework programme ERA-Net project entitled 'European Phytosanitary (statutory plant health) Research Coordination'
EUPHRESCO II	EC seventh framework programme ERA-Net project, the continuation of EUPHRESCO with more partners.
FP7	EU seventh framework programme for Research and Technological Development
Pest	Any species, strain or biotype plant, animal or pathogenic agent injurious to plants or plant products [International Standard on Phytosanitary Measures No. 5, https://www.ippc.int/index.php?id=13399&tx_publication_pi1[showUid]=184195&frompage=13399&type=publication&subtype=&L=0#item] Here: including invasive non-native plants
Phytosanitary research	Research that deals with regulated quarantine pests, emerging pests with the potential to become quarantine pests (organisms new to countries, outbreaks in other countries, non-native invasive species relevant for or associated with, plants) and regulated non-quarantine pests (RNQP) in particular countries

Plant health Regulated/statutory/quarantine plant health; all areas that come within the scope of the Community Plant Health Regime, e.g. pests (including pathogens and invasive weeds, GMO's are excluded. An equivalent term is 'phytosanitary'.

Regulated pest A regulated quarantine pest or a regulated non-quarantine pest [ISPM No. 5]

Research Includes basic and applied research and experimental development as defined by the OECD ([OECD Frascati manual, 2002](#)). Activities excluded from the definition of research are also defined by the Frascati manual (pages 30–46)

Stakeholders Anybody with an interest in plant health who is not a partner of the consortium. This might include governmental organisations as well as research institutes or commercial organisations, or specific individuals or scientists.

Trans-national phytosanitary projects Projects on phytosanitary (regulated plant health) topics involving participants (funders or researchers) from more than one country that are initiated and funded via the EUPHRESCO network.

Modus operandi

1. Purpose

- i. EUPHRESCO is a consortium of research funders (programme owners or managers) of phytosanitary research in Europe and the EPPO region, including other countries as appropriate.
- ii. The consortium aims to enhance coordination and co-operation on phytosanitary research funding in the partner countries, and more widely as appropriate, thereby increasing the benefits from phytosanitary research for all partners and relevant stakeholders. In particular, the outputs of this coordination and cooperation should contribute to:
 - Supporting EU plant health policy development and its implementation
 - Supporting the maintenance and development of phytosanitary science capability
 - Optimising and making best use of national funds for plant health research whilst avoiding duplication
 - Increase communication amongst partners and with other countries, relevant phytosanitary institutions and stakeholders on phytosanitary research.
- iii. The overarching aim is to help protect Europe's agriculture, horticulture, and forestry as well as plants in the environment, from regulated and emerging plant pests through effective trans-national research collaboration, resulting in the maintenance of EU competitiveness.

2. Principle functions of the consortium

- i. The consortium will mainly be based on communication, cooperation and coordination. These will include:
 - Sharing information on national research projects and planning
 - Identifying and prioritising research needs for existing, new or emerging pests of statutory concern that can be addressed through trans-national research (common strategic research agenda)
 - Implementing trans-national projects
 - Advising the Commission on plant health research priorities suitable for EU funding

- Maintaining linkages with key stakeholders and other networks
- Disseminating trans-national research outputs to key stakeholders and policy makers as well as publishing results and activities.

3. Governance and accountability

- i. The consortium will need a steering group to organise and manage the cooperation. It will be guided by a coordinator and a management group.
- ii. The coordinator and the management group will consult with all partners in all relevant decisions and actions as appropriate. The coordinator and the management group are accountable to all partners and vice versa.
- iii. The consortium will be accountable to the COPHS.

4. Coordinator and Management Group

- i. The **coordinator** will lead the collaboration and will act as the head of the consortium. He will be mainly responsible for the:
 - External presentation of the network
 - Transmission of documents and information connected with the activities of the consortium between the partners
 - Initiation of meetings of all network partners or the management group
 - Main contact point to the secretariat (e.g. the EPPO)
- ii. To ensure the collaboration, specific administrative or management tasks have to be taken by some of the partners which will form the **management group**. The tasks (portfolios) will be defined by the collaboration consortium and written down in a collaboration agreement.
- iii. The establishment of the coordinator and the management group will be carried out by all partners.
- iv. Participation in the administration of the consortium will rely on partners volunteering and being nominated or agreed by the wider consortium.
- v. The specific management responsibilities and tasks of the coordinator or members of management groups will be taken on a voluntary basis. The roles of coordinator and management group members, involve increased amount of work. As there will be no financial grants partners volunteering for these positions should make sure that they

are able to deliver this effectively within their own resources for the given period of time.

- vi. Those administrative roles might rotate on a regular basis or change on demand, with agreement of the wider consortium partners. Those partners taking administrative roles would be expected to do this for a minimum of one year up to an agreed maximum period, e.g. three years. Continuation thereafter is possible on partners own wish and the agreement of the wider consortium.

5. Secretariat

- i. A **secretariat** will be needed to handle administrative work, including:
 - a. Comprising the dissemination of important information, e.g. via newsletters
 - b. Hosting of the EUPHRESCO website
 - c. Financial management of the consortium itself
 - d. Assistance in meeting organisation and documentation (e.g. minutes, reporting)
- ii. If possible the secretariat should take over the roles and responsibilities of a call secretariat, including:
 - a. Preparation of research initiation
 - b. Initial identification of topic suggestions
 - c. Coordination of the joining of the listed topic suggestions
 - d. Controlling of the establishment of the long list of topics
 - e. Coordination of the topic coordinator assignment
 - f. Giving administrative support to the production of the short topic description (e.g. providing tools)
 - g. Giving support to the establishment of funding consortia
 - h. Giving support to the decision and agreement of funding mechanisms
 - i. Giving support to the production and signing of commitments
- iii. The secretariat could either located separately, e.g. at the EPPO or at one of the partner countries.
- iv. If the secretariat duties are located at the EPPO, other codes of collaboration might apply that still have to be fixed.

- v. If the secretariat will be located with a partner, same rules apply as for the post as coordinator or management group member.
- vi. Taking over the role as secretariat should be on voluntary basis for a minimum of one year up to an agreed maximum period, e.g. three years. Continuation thereafter is possible on partners own wish and the agreement of the wider consortium.
- vii. If the secretariat is located with a partner, the duties related to the trans-national calls might be outsourced to a specific all secretariat or the funding consortia for the specific projects.

6. Partners

- i. The term "**partners**" refers to all members of the consortium that are public research funders (programme owners or managers) of phytosanitary research in Europe, including potentially other such bodies in third countries (as appropriate). This refers mainly to ministries, governmental bodies or research institutions with their own research budgets, but not organisations that are solely research providers.
- ii. Consortium partners will have complete access to all information and might participate in all discussions on topics and topic descriptions. In return they should contribute to the network by ensuring contact with their own national stakeholders, e.g. via workshops, providing national research agendas, and providing funds for trans-national research as far as they able to do.
- iii. Partners have to finance their own participation in the consortium, i.e. personnel and related costs, e.g. travel and subsistence costs.

7. Advisors

- i. The consortium is expected to establish sufficient contact with organisations which influence plant health policy and with decision makers which should have a certain input into the consortium's activities, i.e. to ensure that trans-national phytosanitary research best serves the needs of plant health policy and is policy led. Such organisations will be referred to as **advisors**.
- ii. Contact with the **European Commission** (EC) is important for the consortium since plant health policy is primarily determined at the European level (via DG SANCO and its Standing Committee on Plant Health); also, alignment with EU-funded research is important (e.g. in EU Framework Programmes). The EC and its appropriate bodies are therefore expected to act as an advisors for the consortium, e.g. via the DG SANCO and DG Research; the EUPHRESCO consortium will therefore both seek and provide advice to the Commission.

- iii. Other important advisors will be the **Standing Committee on Plant Health** (SCPH), the **Chief Officers of Plant Health Services** (COPHS) and the **European Food Safety Association** (EFSA).
- iv. This list can be extended if appropriate.
- v. Advisors might influence activities of the consortium and might participate in meetings and all communication flows. Advisors might have a voice on agreements if they wish.

8. Observers

- i. Organisations, official bodies and institutions with an interest in plant health who are not full partners (principally, but not exclusively, research programme owners or managers) that may wish to join the consortium in the future, or be linked to its activities, might be considered as **observers**. They can be invited to meetings if beneficial and can generally participate in trans-national activities. Observers will not have a voice on agreements but can contribute to discussions. Observers are not restricted to the European region but might come from any country worldwide.

9. Consortiums administration

- i. The consortium requires certain administrative activities to achieve its aims.
- ii. Partners will have one voice if decisions are required; unanimity is favoured but not mandatory.
- iii. For important decisions, consortium meetings are preferred, as they enable partners to communicate directly on important subjects, e.g. trans-national research or common agendas. They might be held in partner countries on a rotating basis approximately once a year. Generally travel costs have to be paid by the partners themselves.
- iv. For other issues, alternative communication mediums should be used as often as possible, email, video or web conferences, interactive websites, Google spreadsheets etc.
- v. Decisions on routine issues can be made by the management group, with the agreement of the other partners.
- vi. Certain consortium aspects or portfolios are linked to financial contributions, e.g. hosting of the website, organisation of meetings etc. The question of financing those activities is not settled so far.

10. Consortiums portfolios

- i. The consortiums portfolios will be guided by the consortiums management group but rely on the active participation of all partners. All management group portfolios might be assumed by a single management group member or can be subscribed to several management group members. This will include:
 - a. The contact to advisors
 - b. Maintenance and updating of a common strategic research agenda. This agenda should reflect national research agendas of the consortium partners and support wider EU Community Plant Health Regime and wider EU-level plant health initiatives, e.g. from the COPHS. It will constitute the actual status quo in the consortiums area concerning identified research needs and gaps. The research agenda relies on the active contribution of partners concerning their national situations and will be updated in a fixed period. The strategic agendas will provide a framework that informs the commissioning of trans-national research.
 - c. Maintenance and updating of the database on national phytosanitary research that has been developed during the ERA-NET EUPHRESCO. It lists projects on phytosanitary topics in the partner countries of the former ERA-NET together with the annual budget. This database has to be maintained and should be updated every year as it supplies important information on conducted, and planned, research. The maintenance of the database will be executed by the management group but support is necessary from all partners.
 - d. Continuation to advise the European Commission on plant health priorities in their framework programs according to the mandate given to EUPHRESCO by the COPHS in June 2007, to ensure effective coordination of transnational and EU-funded research. This will contain the responsibility for identifying research topics appropriate for EU funding in the EU framework programmes and advising on plant health topics suitable for EU funding within the EU Framework Programmes. Furthermore, this will include a good engagement with DG Research, DG SANCO and member states. The consortium will report regularly to the COPHS on identified topics and related activities.
 - e. Evaluation of the consortium's activities after a given period of time, e.g. every three years, to ensure a high quality of network activities and the best value from cooperation. This comprises not only activities of the management group but trans-national cooperation as well. Tools for the evaluation of the different funding mechanisms and cooperation tools have been developed within the EUPHRESCO ERA-Net. Tools for the evaluation of the consortium have to be developed. Ideas could be gathered from other networks or ERA-

NETS¹ or from the recent evaluation of the community plant health regime (CPHR) by the Food Chain Evaluation consortium (FECE).

- f. Establishment of linkages to other networks, ERA-NETs or different organisations e.g. USDA, CABI etc. for enhancing the benefits from cooperation. These contacts are not restricted to plant health but might comprise a broad range of disciplines and research sectors. In addition the consortium should seek regular contact with observers or organisations who are not yet members of EUPHRESCO, e.g. to other countries such as the USA (and the wider QUAD of Australia, New Zealand, Canada and the USA), Africa and Asia, to gain more knowledge about new pests and to align existing research with own projects.
 - g. Maintenance of the consortium's website (internal and external web-pages). The website is currently hosted by the EUPHRESCO coordinator. The maintenance and updating of the website will be a portfolio either assumed by a member of the management group or, depending on the future development one of the tasks taken over by the extern secretariat. The website shall offer possibilities for publication of research results from trans-national projects and information on all network activities including identified topics and topic descriptions.
- ii. This list is not exclusive and might be modified with different or additional activities as needed.
 - iii. Advisors should be informed on important consortium activities and decisions

11. Initiation and implementation of trans-national projects

- i. The initiation, planning, funding and realisation of trans-national projects will be the main task of the EUPHRESCO consortium. The task comprises three different processes as described below which will be coordinated partly by the coordinator respectively the management group and are partly autonomous.
- ii. The process starts with the **identification of relevant topics** for trans-national phytosanitary research. The moderation of topic identification should be assigned to a management group member, supported by the coordinator and the whole management group and other partners as necessary. They assure that

¹ External Evaluation of the ERA-NET SUSPRIME; published by ERA-NET SUSPRIME September 2008
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- complementary with any plant health research funded from the EU framework programme is guaranteed. The topic identification will be influenced by actual problems, policy decisions and needs and in some case by cooperation with the EC and other important plant health bodies or organisations. Topic identification might start any time, as needed, but should aim to be done at least once year as part of a regular routine. Periods and frequency of topic identification processes should comply with needs in the plant health sector and accord to the situation.
- iii. Topics can be proposed by the management group and by any of the partners. Advisors can give advice on topics via the responsible contact in the management group. Discussions on topics and topic selection will be conducted by partners and management group/coordinator and advisors as appropriate. If desired or beneficial, stakeholders can be invited to join the process if appropriate.
 - iv. For each topic, a suitable topic coordinator will be appointed from within the EUPHRESCO Partners. Partners are requested to develop an appropriate topic description using, or adapting, the tools available within the EUPHRESCO toolbox. This process will be guided by the topic coordinator and the secretariat. The topic description should identify the problem and the outcomes required, but not the methods or approaches. The finalised topic description will be distributed internally to all EUPHRESCO partners to enable funders to decide on whether they want to enter the funding consortium and/or to comment on the text, e.g. via a restricted area on the website or via email.
 - v. The following **initiation process** of trans-national projects will be open to all interested parties. Interested funders are requested to get in contact with the topic coordinator to form a funders' consortium. The number of funders involved will not be restricted by the coordinator or the management group. Interested funders do not have to be a partner of the consortium but might be stakeholders.
 - vi. The funding mechanism, e.g. real-common pot, virtual-common pot or non-competitive mechanism, and the project budget will be determined by the funders involved. The revised tool book developed by the EUPHRESCO ERA-NET will be accessible to funders via the website. It provides tested and refined tools and mechanisms for project management including a general roadmap for call management. Relevant tools can be used or adapted by the topic coordinator and the funders' consortium. Funding consortia are responsible for their own call management and/or project initiation.
 - vii. For projects in the non-competitive mechanism, no call will be necessary. General conditions of the cooperation might be fixed via a letter of intent from the funders involved, if desired. The project might be initiated by involved partners with or without a formal proposal; in the case of the former, the research consortium will be required to produce a workplan against the topic description for approval by the

- funding consortium (following the model of the EUPHRESCO non-competitive pilot projects). This non-competitive funding mechanism is mostly suited for short-term projects where there is a limited and clearly identifiable pool of expertise or no specific benefit or requirement for competition, e.g. projects involving diagnostic method development and validation through ring tests, or projects in response to emergency situations. The applicability of this kind of funding for long-term projects has still to be analysed.
- viii. For competitively-let projects funded via the real-common pot or virtual-common pot mechanism, a call will be necessary. In the *virtual-common pot (VP)*, funders only pay for the involvement of researchers from their own country. The research consortium therefore only includes researchers from those countries providing funds. In the *real-common pot (RP)*, the budget is pooled and there can be a transnational flow of funds. This means that applicants do not necessarily have to be a consortium of different nationalities but might consist of only one organisation or of different organisations from the same or different countries, including (potentially) research organisations outside of those countries providing the funding.
 - ix. The **implementation** of the individual trans-national projects will not be steered by the consortium. It will be solely the responsibility of interested funders (funding consortium).
 - x. The funders' consortium will prepare the call and decide on a call secretariat (if necessary), and divide necessary tasks between the members of the funders' consortium.
 - xi. To ensure a high quality of the commissioned research, proposals may be evaluated by peer review. The decision on the need for peer review of proposals and the evaluation processes, e.g. the number and choice of peer reviewers, will be the responsibility of the involved funders. Settlements on legal arrangements, contract negotiations and forms are likewise the responsibility of the funders. To avoid ambiguity the legal settlements should contain arrangements about later publication of results and intellectual property.
 - xii. Results from trans-national projects initiated in the frame of the consortium should be made accessible to all partners. All conducted research should guarantee high quality and best value for the raised budget.

12. Supplementing documents

- i. This modus operandi can be supplemented by several documents.
- ii. The EUPHRESCO **collaboration agreement** is a document that lays out the roles of responsibilities of partners in the consortium. It is not a legal document and partners

simply indicate their intention to fulfil their roles and responsibilities via a signed **Letter of Intent**. It helps ensure the continuity of the consortium's tasks.

- iii. The EUPHRESCO **common strategic research agenda** reflects a survey on current phytosanitary problems for the mid-term and long-term research aims of the consortium. It should be revised every 3 to 5 years.
- iv. The EUPHRESCO **toolbook** is a collection of processes and tools that facilitate trans-national research. It will be revised and adapted as required and will be published on the website.

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